

A Study on Marketing of Milk and Its Products from Non Coperative Milk Producers in Theni and Madurai Districts

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Abstract

Indian dairy is the single largest contributor to India's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) contributing more than 5 per cent of the GDP. As many as 70 million small farming households, one out of every two rural households, are involved in dairying. About 80 per cent of milk produced in the country is handled by the unorganized sector and the remaining 20 per cent is shared equally by co-operative and private sectors for processing with varying degree of product-mix. The parameters of marketing like marketing cost, marketing margin, marketing efficiency etc. This study attempts to find out the socio, economic, demographic and familial profile of the milk producers and to analyse the marketing strategies of milk and its products. The researcher has collected the data from milk producers of Theni and Madurai districts for the study. The primary data were collected through well-structured questionnaire using stratified random Sampling. The researcher has adopted convenient sampling and collected data from 200 respondents for the study during November 2018 to December 2018.

Majority of the customers have been distributed with products proximately after placing an order however, it appears that a segment of customer could not get the product on in time. In order to satisfy the needs of all customers to get the products timely, supplementary provisions have to be made by the dairy industries such as keeping the channels open for extra time.

Keywords: Dairy industries, Milk products, Distribution Channel, supplementary, efficiency, marketing cost, co-operative.

Introduction

"The science and art of exploring, creating, and delivering value to satisfy the needs of a target market at a profit. Marketing identifies unfulfilled needs and desires. It defines measures and quantifies the size of the identified market and the profit potential. It pinpoints which segments the company is capable of serving best and it designs and promotes the appropriate products and services." -Dr. Philip Kotler

Milk is the most important supplement for the human life. Cow's milk is the most important substitute for breast feeding. Denmark ranks first in the world for milk production. In India AMUL is most leading

milk producer in our country, it is otherwise known as Anand Milk Union Limited. Kurien was the founder of AMUL and called as the father of white revolution. India produces 17 million tonnes in 1950-51 to about 104.84 million tonnes by 2007-08. Whereas world's milk production is increasing at the rate of 1 per cent per annum, Indian dairy is the single largest contributor to India's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) contributing more than 5 per cent of the GDP. As many as 70 million small farming households, one out of every two rural households, are involved in dairying. About 80 per cent of milk produced in the country is handled by the unorganized sector and the remaining 20 per cent is shared equally by co-operative and private sectors for processing with varying degree of product-mix. The parameters of marketing like marketing cost, marketing margin, marketing efficiency etc. depends on the structure of milk and milk products market. Marketing costs and marketing margins reflect the efficiency of the system to a great extent. The analysis of marketing costs and margins of dairy plants would help in reducing the unwarranted costs in marketing of dairy products (Babu.D, 2010). Dairying is one of the expanding branches that came out of the Green Revolution. It is an agro-based industry, expanding very fast throughout the world. A decade ago only 5 per cent of the milk produces came into the dairies, whereas today, it is 10 per cent and it is increasing. Recent report by the Ministry of Agriculture reveals that the Dairy industry has the potential to offer about 4.2 crore jobs per year. The demand for milk products would increase as a result of increase in national GDP. In order to meet the demand, it is essential to have a consistent increase in milk production, which will be possible on successful implementation of "Operation Flood" and evolution or new animal breed. The importance of dairying lies not only in production of milk, but in its capacity to bring about significant changes in the socio-economic structure of rural economy. Its role in employment-generation is well recognized. It has provided numerous small/marginal farmers and agricultural labourers with supplementary employment and a regular source of income. Dairying and its related activities create jobs equivalent to about 25 million a year. The significant role played by the co-operatives in stimulation of dairying has also proved to be an important source of progress (Edhayavarman.C.S., 2011).

Benefits of Milk and Its Products

Milk is the most important nutrition for the human life. It is called as the best substitute for mother's milk. Cow's milk contains calcium which helps in building bones and also in the growth of the teeth in infants. Many studies revealed that consumption of milk helps in development of brain and muscle. Drinking in milk will increase the blood pallets. The condensed milk is used in cooking as the main ingredients. The milk products like curd is used as increase the fat content in human body. The butter milk is used as coolant in human bodies during summer times. The cheese, butter, ice creams are the by- product of milk which increases the body weight. The milk drinks like rose milk, badam drink, pista drink and chocolate drink is the most famous refresher drink.

Review of Literature

Babu.D, (2010), has studied the "Marketing of Milk and Milk Products in Organised Sector of Salem District (Tamil Nadu)". In their study they tried to estimate the cost of milk procurement of co-operative and private dairy plants. They have studied the processing and manufacturing costs of dairy products by the co-operative and private sector plants. They have worked out the marketing costs and marketing efficiency of organised marketing channels. They identified the constraints faced at milk procurement, processing and marketing levels. The data was collected from Salem district. The results revealed that Lack of infrastructure was the principal constraint at both the cooperative society and collection centre level. Poor road conditions for milk haulage were the main constraint among milk transporters of co-operative plant. Underutilization of transport vehicles

ranked first position among private milk transporters. Lack of skilled manpower was the important constraint at cooperative chilling centres whereas under-utilisation of capacity was found to be the main constraint at private chilling centres.

Ashraf Imam, M N Zadeh, and Laxmi Rani Dubey, (2011), have investigated “Dairy Marketing Strategies in the Context of Globalization: Issues and Challenges”. In their study they tried to analyse the marketing Strategies which focus on the actions the dairy industry needs to take to influence perceptible from the dairy farming system to the world. The results revealed that proper production, processing and marketing infrastructure, should be done which is capable of meeting international quality requirements.

Christine Bickelhaupt and Cynthia Verwer, (2013), have undergone study titled “Investigating Marketing Opportunities for Dairy Products from Dam Rearing Systems”, In their study they have tried to find out the opinion of relevant stakeholders towards it, specifically with respect to their perception towards the added value of the product. They have collected the data through well-structured questionnaire by the means of random sampling. The results revealed that all respondents across stakeholders stress the positive effects on animal welfare, animal health and behaviour. In particular, dam rearing systems are considered to have positive impact on the animals ‘immune defence and on the mother-cows ‘longevity and fertility.

Franklin John.S, Senith.S and Reshma Ravindran (2013), have publicized “Branding is the solution for product differentiation in Indian Dairy Industry”, in their study they have tried to investigate the influence of Milk brand rating and different dimensions of milk brand. For their study the data were collected from 325 consumers from Tamil Nadu, who are all using branded milk. The questionnaires were given to 500 consumers who are all using branded milk.. The results revealed that statistically significant differences were found in the Milk brand rating and the different brand dimensions like salience, Imagery Judgment, feelings and resonance and there is no statistically significant difference in dimension performance and Milk brand rating.

Ayyappa Naik Nenavath.S, (2013), has reviewed the study titled “A Study on Marketing Effectiveness of Sales Promotion Strategies on The Dairy Industry”, in his study he has intended to to evaluate the effectiveness of the strategies of the Sangam Dairy regarding sales promotion of the products and assess the impact of sales promotion of the Sangam Dairy for its products based on the opinions of the customers. The present study has employed stratified Random sampling technique for the selection of the sample towns’ respondents. The study has selected two municipalities at random accounting for 10 per cent of the total municipalities. One is Guntur Municipal Corporation and other is Ponnuru municipality. The study reveals that in two towns of Guntur and Ponnuru, the majority of respondents stated that the leakage problems are higher in packaging. The management of Sangam dairy organization has to identify well in advance areas where leakage is occurring and has to take corrective steps at the production level, quality control level, transportation side and lastly, at the time of delivery of products to the customer. The analysis brings out a fact that there’s mixed opinion among the respondents as to the type of quality required.

Kaushlendra Vikram Mishra and Goyal.C.K, (2015), has examined “Marketing Channels Used by Small-scale Milk Producers: A Study in Azamgarh District”. In this study they have intended to understand advantage and disadvantage of different milk marketing channels, find out marketing channels available for small-scale milk producers and to understand strength and weakness of small-scale milk producers. The study has conducted at Azamgarh district of Uttar Pradesh. The present study covers 100 households in the district. Using multistage random sampling a sample of 100, households representing various socio economic groups have been selected. The results revealed that due to having small amount of surplus milk, largely the milk producers (56 per cent) sell their milk directly to the consumers or neighbour. Here on the one hand, easily availability of

feed, fodder and skilled manpower strengthen the supply of milk. On the other hand the improved purchasing power of consumers and no near substitute of milk make the demand of milk very high. The low productivity of milk animals, perishable nature of milk, no quality control over the milk, inadequate cold chain facilities, low label of surplus milk and lack of proper marketing channels are the main weakness of the small-scale milk producers in the research area. Availability of milk powder and liquid milk tetra pack produced by multinationals and big milk co-operatives are competing up to some extent with fresh milk. Small-scale milk producers are unable to compete with these giant dairy firms and multinational brands. Moreover, manufacturing of value added milk products make the condition worse for the small holders. Due to increasing per capita income, there is expanding market for fresh milk as well as traditional dairy products. Besides this liberalized policies in dairy sector make more avenues in front of small-scale milk producers.

Jaikanth.C.M, (2016), analysed “Global Marketing Strategy and Constraints of Indian Dairy Industry”. In his study he tried to find out the activity of the private companies is in the process of converting our unorganised dairy sector into organised industry. The data is collected from the different government reports and news collected from the various newspapers and magazines. Certain references are also taken from the different scholarly research articles published in the field. The results revealed that there is a wealth of untapped business in dairy industry in India. First there should be focus on increasing quality milk production per animal in a scientific way which can conserve huge amount of economy spent on unproductive animals. The focus should be more to produce highly profitable value added dairy products in compliance with international standards so that they can be easily exported and marketed without any resistance.

Kiran.R,(2017) has investigated “Promotion and Distribution Strategy of Dairy Industry”. In her study she tried to find out the performance of dairy industry in their promotional strategy and distribution network. The present study is designed to cover the total population of dairy units in Junagadh district. The list of dairy units in Junagadh has been obtained from the district dairy development office Junagadh. There are 13 dairy units in Junagadh district. Purpose sampling method is adopted to select the sample dairy units. For the study, 2 cooperative, 1 private, 1 public limited and 1 primary dairy cooperative were selected. The results revealed that The most preferred media include radio, newspapers, local TV channels and point of purchase advertisements. The advertising budget is decided on the basis of affordability method. They increase the surveyed dairy units have developed the good brand image. The sales force is utilized to persuade the distributors and retailers to push the sales of specific dairy unit. They adopt timely delivery and marketing assistance to the distributors and retailers to promote the sales. All the dairy units do not use sales promotion tools. There is need for better distribution network in Junagadh district, after assessing the existing situation.

Objectives of the Study

1. To identify the socio, economic, demographic, familial profile of the milk producers.
2. To analyse the marketing strategies of milk and its products.

Scope of the Study

This study attempts to find out the socio, economic, demographic and familial profile of the milk producers and to analyse the marketing strategies of milk and its products.

Research Methodology

Profile Area of the Study

The researcher has collected the data from milk producers of Theni and Madurai districts for the study.

Source of Data Collection

The primary data were collected through well-structured questionnaire using stratified random Sampling.

Sample size and Sample Design

The researcher has adopted convenient sampling and collected data from 200 respondents for the study during November 2018 to December 2018.

Tools for Data Collection

The researcher has adopted percentage analysis and Chi-square test for the study

Limitations of the Study

1. The study was confined and limited to Theni and Madurai Districts only due to time limitations.
2. The study was done based on pure primary data. The recording over the data is true as per the representation given by the respondents only. Some of them were in hurry and gave the data as per compulsion.
3. The data were collected from those farmers those who are willing to provide the data for research purpose.

Background profile of the respondents

Demographic Profile

From the table 01 it is clear that most of the respondents (50 percent) belongs to the age group of 31 to 40 years followed by the age group of 41 to 50 years (25 percent) 21 to 30 and 50 years and above with 12.5 percent each. It is also clear that majority of respondents are male followed by female with 62.5 and 37.5 percent respectively.

Table 1 Demographic Profile

(N= 200)

Demographic Profile	Number of Respondents
Age	
21 to 30 years	25 (12.5)
31 to 40 years	100 (50)
41 to 50 years	50 (25)
Above 50 years	25 (12.5)
Gender	
Male	125 (62.5)
Female	75 (37.5)

Source: Compiled from the field data (2018)

Note: Figures in parantheses are percentage to the coloum total.

Social Profile

From the below table it is clear that most of the respondents belongs to backward caste with 60 percent, followed by SC/ST and Most Backward Caste with 17.5 and 12.5 percent. As per religion most of the respondent belongs to Hindu religion with 85 percent followed by Christian and Muslim with 10 and 5 percent. Most of the respondents belong to rural area with 75 percent followed by semi urban and urban area with 20 and 05 percent respectively.

Table 2 Social Profile of the Respondents

(N=200)

Social Profile	Number of Respondents
Caste	
Forward Caste	20 (10)
Backward Caste	120 (60)
Most Backward Caste	25 (12.5)
Scheduled Caste/ Scheduled Tribe	35 (17.5)
Religion	
Hindu	170 (85)
Christians	20 (10)
Muslims	10 (05)
Residential Status	
Urban area	10 (05)
Semi Urban area	40 (20)
Rural area	150 (75)

Source: Compiled from the field data (2018)

Note: Figures in parantheses are percentage to the coloum total.

Familial Profile

As per the Table 03 it is clear that most of the respondents are married with 87.5 percent and remaining are unmarried with 12.5 percent. Most of the respondents live in joint family with 75 percent and remaining in nuclear family with 25 percent. Most of the respondents have four members with 75 percent followed by five members and more than six members with 10 and 05 percent respectively. It is also clear that maximum numbers of earning members in the family are two with 62.5 percent followed by more than four members and three members with 17.5 and 12.5 percent respectively.

Table 3 Familial Profile of the respondents

(N=200)

Familial Profile	Number of Respondents
Marital Status	
Married	175 (87.5)
Unmarried	25 (12.5)
Type of the Family	
Joint family	150 (75)
Nuclear family	50 (25)
Size of the Family	
Two members	02 (01)
Three members	10 (05)
Four members	150 (75)
Five members	20 (10)

More than six members	18 (09)
Number of earning family members	
One members	15 (08)
Two members	125 (62.5)
Three members	25 (12.5)
More than four members	35 (17.5)

Source: Compiled from the field data (2018)

Note: Figures in parantheses are percentage to the coloum total.

Economic profile

It is clear from the below table that most of the respondents earn Rs 2 Lakhs and above as their annual income with 75 percent followed by their annual income Rs 1,00,000 to 1,50,000 is 10 percent , and Rs 1,50,000 to 2,00,000 with 7.5 percent . It is also clear that most of the respondents spends their annual expenditure about Rs 75,000 to 1,00,000 (75 percent). Followed by Rs 50,000 to 75,000 (10 percent) and Rs 1,00,000 and above with 7.5 percent.

Table 4 Economic Profile of the respondents

(N=200)

Economic Profile	Number of Respondents
Annual Income in Rupees	
Below 50,000	05 (2.5)
50,000 to 1,00,000	10 (05)
1,00,000 to 1,50,000	20 (10)
1,50,000 to 2,00,000	15 (7.5)
2,00,000 and above	150 (75)
Annual Expenditure in Rupees	
up to 25,000	05 (2.5)
25,000 to 50,000	10 (05)
50,000 to 75,000	20 (10)
75,000 to 1,00,000	150 (75)
1,00,000 and above	15 (7.5)

Source: Compiled from the field data (2018)

Note: Figures in parantheses are percentage to the coloum total

Educational profile

It is clear from the table below that most of the respondents have no formal education with 62.5 percentage followed by the respondents with education up to graduation and SSLC with 15 and 10 percent respectively.

Table 5 Educational Profile of the Respondents

(N=200)

Educational Profile	Number of respondents
Unmarried Status	NA
No formal education	125 (62.5)
up to Secondary	20 (10)
Higher Secondary	10 (05)
Diploma	15 (7.5)
Graduate	30 (15)
Post Graduate	0
Professional Degree	0

Source: Compiled from the field data (2018)

Note: Figures in parentheses are percentage to the column total.

Marketing of Milk and Its Products

It is clear from the above table that caste and type of family are the variables which are found to highly insignificant even though they have association with the variables with 0.763 and 0.980. The variables which are found to be significant at 5percent level are gender and residential status with 0.016 each. The variables which are found to be significant at 1 percent level are age (0.002), marital status and annual expenditure with 0.001 each. All other variable are found to be highly significant.

Table 6 Association of Marketing of Milk and Its Products

Socio Economic and Demographic Variables	Chi-Square Value with Proposal Form	Level of Significance
Age	53.655	0.002
Gender	25.371	0.016
Caste	25.052	0.763
Religion	69.687	0.000
Marital Status	29.955	0.001
Type of family	04.691	0.980
Number of family members	162.755	0.000
Number of earning family members	92.866	0.000
Residential Status	39.493	0.016
Annual Income	99.093	0.000
Annual Expenditure	75.192	0.001
Education of the self	168.374	0.000
Education of the spouse	138.297	0.000
Occupation of the self	107.297	0.000
Occupation of the spouse	162.839	0.000

Conclusion

The analysis brings out a point that there's mixed view among the respondents as to the type of quality required. By taking the evidences into account the dairy industries has to yield and mete out the milk products as per the demand of respondents such as fatness as well as freshness and even the element of fat content also. Majority of the customers have been distributed with products proximately after placing an order however, it appears that a segment of customer could not get the product on in time. In order to satisfy the needs of all customers to get the products timely, supplementary provisions have to be made by the dairy industries such as keeping the channels open for extra time.

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